

Universities Academic Staff Developing Effects On Palestinian Society Development

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Purpose – The purpose of the study is Examine Universities academic staff Developing Effects on Palestinian society development, to acknowledge if there are statistical differences due to gender, place of residence, degree, Collage, and academic level.

Design/methodology/approach – The researcher developed Questionnaire of 24 items and administered it to 400students from Palestine Technical University KadoorieThe study used a descriptive approach to analyze the collected data.

Findings – According to the student’s perspective, the average Universities academic staff Developing Effects on Palestinian society development is 3.54. There were no statistically significant differences in due to gender, place of residence, degree, and collage..

Originality/value – The author hopes that her results will inspire other researchers to conduct more research in this field and will help universities realize the importance of professional development for their employees, which will be reflected in improving and developing educational training, which in turn will lead to improving the level of students.

Key words: *Professional development, academic staff, Palestine Technical University, Palestinian society, society development.*

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Introduction

Professional development represents an important and essential input of the educational process, and it is concerned with improving the performance of workers in all educational institutions, including educational leaders, administrators and academics (Faeq, 2020), which makes them able to carry out their roles and work requirements efficiently and effectively, and with the development of the basic functions of the university and its endeavor to achieve comprehensive quality and face future challenges (Pham, 2021).

The concept of professional development has spread in developed and developing countries of the world alike (Iosif et al. 2023), in order to make the best use of academic staff members and strengthen their capabilities, and to enhance the role of the university in achieving one of its functions, which is community service (Besty, 2014)

This broader concept means that professional development is the means through which academic staff and leaders at the university can acquire and enhance their knowledge, skills and beliefs (Somadina et al. 2023), necessary to provide high educational and administrative levels in the interest of society and lead to its continuous and permanent development (Muhammad, 2016)

Institutions of higher education are the locomotive of development in its various fields (Yaqub et al. 2020). They also represent houses of expertise that provide the various sectors of work and production with what they need of qualified cadres in various fields. The university, in turn, does this through three main areas: teaching, scientific research, and community service (Pham, 2021)

Professional development helps in improving the quality of professional life within educational institutions (Bo-Ruey, 2016), providing its employees with more experiences and information that contribute to raising their intellectual, cultural and professional level, developing their readiness to take on new roles, and developing their skills (Allison, 2013), whether by providing them with multiple skills or providing them with values appropriate to the nature of their profession and their current and future roles. In the end, it serves the local community in which these institutions are located (Ahmad & Jameel, 2021).

Professional development, in general, is an intended process through which programs provide the academic staff member with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes that enable him to absorb the developments of his advanced profession, and develop accordingly to meet the changes facing modern societies (Jacob et al. 2021).

And if higher education institutions are the locomotive of development, then the member of the academic staff is the main engine of this locomotive (Mwesigwa et al. 2020), and to the extent of his quality and the level of his performance, the success of the educational institution in performing its role in leading society in various sectors towards progress, advancement and well-being (Adejare et al. 2020).

Supporting professional development is considered one of the most important tasks entrusted to those working in the field of education (Vu & Nwachukwu, 2020), because it is the most valuable resource for any country, so it must provide it with time and resources that help it grow and develop to reach the ranks of specialists (Bingwa & Ngibe, 2021).

Therefore, higher education institutions around the world have taken care of the need to organize many continuous professional development programs for academic staff members and educational leaders in them (Kirkova-Bogdanova, (2021), in order to develop and organize their investment capacity, and increase their absorptive capacity in light of their policies, which express their ability to benefit from professional development programs (Barry, 2023)

Gaps in the Literature

Many previous studies have studied the issue of human resources development, as this concept has received the attention of many researchers in various fields, and the palestinian society has received many studies that have studied ways of its development and development, but the researcher did not find sufficient research that covered the point of view of palestine technical university students about this topic, hence the idea of this article.

The originality of the present study

Palestinian universities are one of the most important tools for change in the prevailing thinking pattern, and the real field for building and shaping the personalities of students in them, and providing the community with the outputs on which it is based on its operation, development, and meeting its needs, and given that the members of the academic staff are very influential in the process of preparing university students who form the pillar of its rise and development, interest in their development and the development of their knowledge, experience and skills is one of the things taken for granted if the university is to fulfill its mission in serving the community to society development.

Aims Of The Study

The purpose of the study is Examine Universities academic staff Developing Effects on Palestinian society development, to acknowledge if there are statistical differences due to gender, place of residence, degree, Collage, and academic level

Research Question

The Main Question: what is Universities academic staff Developing Effects on Palestinian society development?

Based on the main question the following sub-question formed:

Is there a difference in Universities academic staff Developing Effects on Palestinian society development due to gender, place of residence, degree, Collage, and academic level?

Study hypothesis:

1. There are no statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of Universities academic staff Developing Effects on Palestinian society development due to gender.
2. There are no statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of Universities academic staff Developing Effects on Palestinian society development due to place of residence.
3. There are no statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of Universities academic staff Developing Effects on Palestinian society development due to degree.
4. There are no statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of Universities academic staff Developing Effects on Palestinian society development due to Collage.
5. There are no statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of Universities academic staff Developing Effects on Palestinian society development due to academic level.

The significance of the study:

The importance of the study appears in being related to an important topic of the modern era in terms of measuring the impact of the development of university employees on the development of the local community, the presidents of Palestinian universities and researchers interested in community development through the development of university employees may benefit from this study.

Definition of terms:

Palestine Technical University Kadoorie: It is "one of the institutions of higher education in Palestine. It is the first and only public university in the West Bank affiliated to the Ministry of Education and Higher Education. It was established in 1930 as an agricultural school to serve the Palestinian community and then developed into a college that offers diploma programs in many disciplines. It turned into a college University / is the Palestine Technical College Khadouri under the Palestinian National Authority to offer technical programs at its various levels (diploma and bachelor's), and on 8/28/2007 during the era of the Deputy Minister of Minister "Minister of Higher Education" Dr. The National Authority for Accreditation, Quality and Quality and His Excellency the Minister of Education and Higher Education (<http://www.ptuk.edu.ps/>)

Development academic staff members: is defined as the professional characteristics that relate to the university professor's ability to plan, prepare and implement educational processes, take care of preparing lectures, and use modern teaching methods that contribute to the development of students' learning skills. (Ivanenko et al, 2022).

Methods (design of the study):

The current study adopted the descriptive analytical approach. After collecting the data, the researchers used the analytical-statistical method to answer the question of the study and interpreted the results.

Population and sample of the study:**Population of the study:**

The population of the study consisted of all students at Palestine technical university. The total Number was (1761).

Sample of the Study:

From this population a (400) sample of students from a random cluster were chosen to respond to the questionnaire.

Table (1): Statistical description of the research sample according to demographic variables

Demographic Variables	Frequency	
Gender	Male	195
	Female	205
	Total	400
Place of residence	Camp	75
	Village	232
	City	93
	Total	400
degree	Diploma	25
	Pachalore	57
	Total	62
Collage	Media	241
	Arts	15
	Sports	400
	Management	135
	Technology and computer	265
Total	400	

Figure (1): research sample according to demographic variables

Instruments of the study:

The researcher developed Questionnaire, to examine Universities academic staff Developing Effects on Palestinian society development, it consists of two sections. The first section included personal information about the respondents. The second section included (24) items, to investigate Universities academic staff Developing Effects on Palestinian society development, The researcher developed the questionnaire with 3-point Likert scales ranging from strongly agree - strongly disagree. The questionnaires distributed to (450) students.

Validity of instruments:

To ensure that the content of the questionnaire was valid, it handed to a jury of professional doctors in the field at Palestine technical university, The Panel of judges asked to evaluate the opportunities of the instrument to the whole purpose of the study. They accepted the items and the parts of the questionnaire, but they asked the researchers to follow some modifications. The researchers took these recommendations into amount before issuing the final draft of the tool, and then the instrument distributed to the subject of the study.

Reliability of instruments:

Cronbach's Alpha Value for the questionnaire was (91.2%) which is appropriate for the purposes of the study.

Procedures of the study:

The study carried out in the following manner:

1. The relevant literature reviewed to establish the theoretical background of the study.
2. The population identified and the samples selected on which the instruments applied.
3. The questions of the study put up, depending on previous studies.
4. The reliability and validity of the instruments approved.
5. The researcher distributed the instruments on students.
6. The instrument distributed and gathered in the Second semester of the scholastic year 2022-2023.
7. The data was gathered and analyzed by using SPSS program.
8. The researcher explained the information to reveal whether the outcomes agree or disagree with previous studies.

Variables of the study:

1. **Independent variables:** Gender (Female/Male), Place of residence (City/Village/Camp), Degree (diploma/Pachalore), Collage (Arts/Business/Applied Arts/Media).
2. **Dependent variables:** Universities academic staff Developing Effects on Palestinian society development.

Data analysis

In order to analyze the data, the researchers used statistical Package for social science (SPSS), descriptive statistics (means, frequencies, percentage, and Std. Deviation) and inferential statistics. (Independent T-test, one-way ANOVA, LSD and Cronbach Alpha).

Results and discussion

To determine Universities academic staff Developing Effects on Palestinian society development, and in order to interpret the results, the following arithmetic means and percentages adopted:

An arithmetic means of (1.8–2.59) or (36–51.9%) indicates a low score.

The mean (2.60 – 3.39) or (52 – 67.9 %) indicates a Moderate score.

An arithmetic means of (3.40 –4.19) or (68 – 83.9%) indicates a high degree.

Results related to the first question:

What is developing academic staff at universities effects on developing palestinian society?

To answer this question, the researcher calculated the arithmetic means and standard deviations of the study sample's estimates of Universities academic staff Developing Effects on Palestinian society development for each paragraph of the tool and for the total score. Table (2) shows that.

TABLE (2): MEANS, STD. DEV. AND DEGREES OF THE ITEMS OF THE QUESTIONNAIRE.

#	Item	Mean	Std. Dev.	Degree
15	Update and develop the knowledge and skills of academic staff members in the field of community service.	4.14	1.17	High
24	Members of the academic staff participate in holding seminars and workshops for community members that meet their different needs.	4.12	1.17	High
8	Planning professional development programs for academic staff members is linked to achieving the general goals of the community.	4.11	1.18	High
17	Organizes and supervises courses in the field of literacy and adult education.	4.09	1.3	High
23	Members of the academic staff participate in holding training courses for members of the community.	4.94	1.32	High
2	The Foundation provides a scientific climate that supports scientific research activities aimed at serving the community.	3.91	1.24	High
16	Design programs to develop the skills of workers in local community institutions.	3.69	1.31	High
3	Members of the academic staff participate in research that deals with many creative ideas that serve the community.	3.69	1.13	High
6	Appropriate budget shall be approved to provide the necessary material resources for professional development programs aimed at developing scientific research skills.	3.66	1.24	High
14	Encourages creativity and innovation in all fields of work of an academic staff member with regard to community service.	3.6	1.29	High
12	There are interdisciplinary research teams made up of members of academic staff and members of the local community.	3.48	1.16	High
7	College academic staff gain the trust and support of community institutions.	3.46	1.25	High
10	Meetings are held between members of the academic staff and members of the local community in order to exchange experiences as a form of professional development.	3.45	1.16	High
1	The research of the academic staff is related to the problems of society.	3.37	1.06	Moderate
13	Academic staff members update their courses according to the needs of the community.	3.34	1.25	Moderate
19	It helps academic staff to benefit the local community from what they have gained from the professional development programs offered to them.	3.45	1.13	Moderate
4	In his scientific production, the academic staff member adopts contemporary research methodologies and methods that keep pace with the problems of contemporary society.	3.32	1.03	Moderate

18	Encourages members of the academic staff to hold high-level training courses for members of the local community.	3.18	1.31	Moderate
21	It allows academic staff members to work as volunteers with local community organizations in order to benefit from their experiences as a form of professional development.	3.14	1.02	Moderate
20	It allows its specialized cadres to contribute to the development of local community institutions.	3.13	1.23	Moderate
9	Academic staff build long-term relationships with their students.	3.08	1.22	Moderate
22	Scientific and applied cooperation agreements are concluded with local community institutions.	3.08	1.02	Moderate
5	It adopts strategic planning for professional development programs to raise the level of its academic staff members in the field of scientific research.	2.8	1.26	Moderate
11	Seminars and scientific conferences are organized to solve community problems as a form of professional development for academic staff members.	2.8	1.02	Moderate
26	Total	3.54	0.09	High

Results in table (2) show that developing academic staff at universities Effects on developing Palestinian society was High, with a mean of (3.54) over/out of (5).

Results related to the second question:

Is there a difference in Universities academic staff Developing Effects on Palestinian society development due to gender, place of residence, Degree, and Collage?

To answer this question, the researchers investigated the following hypothesis:

Results related to the first hypothesis:

There are no statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of Universities academic staff Developing Effects on Palestinian society development due to gender.

To test this hypothesis, the researcher used independent t-test as table (3) shows: The results of independent t-test for the differences in participant's responses related to Universities academic staff Developing Effects on Palestinian society development due to gender.

TABLE (3): RESULTS OF THE INDEPENDENT T-TEST FOR GENDER VARIABLE.

gender	Mean	Std. Dev.	Std. Error Mean	Sig.
male	2.95	.420	1.93	0.06
female	2.75	.370		

The results in table (3) show that the level of significance for the differences in participant's responses related to Universities academic staff Developing Effects on Palestinian society development due to gender is (0.06) this means that there are no statistically significant differences at ($\alpha < 0.05$), in favor of female students, Thus, the hypothesis is accepted.

Results related to the second hypothesis:

There are no statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of Universities academic staff Developing Effects on Palestinian society development due to place of residence.

To test this hypothesis, the researcher used one-way ANOVA- test, table (4) shows: The results of one-way ANOVA- test for the differences in participant's responses related to Universities academic staff Developing Effects on Palestinian society development due to place of residence.

TABLE (4): The Results Of Anova- Test For The Differences In The Participant's Responses Related To Universities Academic Staff Developing Effects On Palestinian Society Development Due To Place Of Residence.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	0.1010	3	0.0340	0.20	0.89
Within Groups	10.287	61	0.1690		
Total	10.388	64			

The results in this table (4) show that the level of significance for the differences in the participant's responses related to Universities academic staff Developing Effects on Palestinian society development due to place of residence is (0.89) this means that there are no statistically significance differences at ($\alpha < 0.05$). Thus, the hypothesis accepted.

Results related to the third hypothesis:

There are no statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of Universities academic staff Developing Effects on Palestinian society development due to degree.

To test this hypothesis, the researcher used independent t-test as table (5) shows: The results of independent t-test for the differences in participant's responses related to Universities academic staff Developing Effects on Palestinian society development due to degree.

TABLE (5): RESULTS OF THE INDEPENDENT T-TEST FOR DEGREE VARIABLE.

degree	Mean	Std. Dev.	Std. Error Mean	Sig.
Diploma	2.87	0.400	0.8180	0.41
Pachalore	2.79	0.400		

The results in table (5) show that the level of significance for the differences in participant's responses related to Universities academic staff Developing Effects on Palestinian society development due to degree is (0.41) this means that there are no statistically significant differences at ($\alpha < 0.05$). Thus, the hypothesis is accepted.

Results related to the fourth hypothesis:

There are no statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of Universities academic staff Developing Effects on Palestinian society development due to Collage.

To test this hypothesis, the researchers used one-way ANOVA- test, table (6) shows: The results of one-way ANOVA- test for the differences in participant's responses related to Universities academic staff Developing Effects on Palestinian society development due to Collage.

TABLE (6): The Results Of Anova- Test For The Differences In The Participant's Responses Related To Universities Academic Staff Developing Effects On Palestinian Society Development Due To Collage.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	0.072	2	0.0360	0.2160	0.800
Within Groups	10.316	62	0.1660		
Total	10.388	64			

The results in this table (6) show that the level of significance for the differences in the participant's responses related to related to Universities academic staff Developing Effects on Palestinian society development due to Collage is (0.80) this means that there are no statistically significance differences at ($\alpha < 0.05$). Thus, the hypothesis accepted.

Results

The study results showed that the moral and cultural values of university students and their role in achieving educational policies in Palestinian universities was High, with a mean of (3.54) over/out of (5). The result also revealed that there were no statistically significant differences in due to gender, place of residence, degree, and collage.

Dissection Of The Results Of The Study

1. The researcher attributed The High Universities academic staff Developing Effects on Palestinian society development to the following: The Universities academic staff are the ones who pass on the skills, values, and principles on which the society is based, and in order to provide students with the appropriate skills for rapid change, the faculty members must be continuously developed, and they must also be given the necessary expertise to pass on the values and principles that contribute to the development of the Palestinian society.
2. The researcher attributed that there are no statistically significant differences with Universities academic staff Developing Effects on Palestinian society development due to gender to the following: the members of the study realize the effect of developing staff members at the university in serving the local community, as development is in the interest of the community and brings great benefit to it because of what it entails in developing the knowledge, skills and capabilities of staff members, which in turn is reflected in the performance of students who They are the main tributary of the community by the university.
3. The researcher attributed that there are no statistically significant differences with Universities academic staff Developing Effects on Palestinian society development due to place of residence to the following: The study sample agreed on the impact of staff development at the university on the development of the local community, regardless of their place of residence, as development benefits the community and students, through the activities

it offers that enrich the capabilities of staff and students, which is beneficial to the development and development of society.

4. The researcher attributed that there are no statistically significant differences with Universities academic staff Developing Effects on Palestinian society development due to degree to the following: There is no difference in the opinions of the study sample about the impact of staff development at the university on the development of the local community, as students, with different faculties and degrees, saw that there is a need for staff development at the university to achieve the benefit and development of the community.
5. The researcher attributed that there are no statistically significant differences with the Universities academic staff Developing Effects on Palestinian society development due to collage to the following: All members of the study sample from their various faculties are aware of the impact of the development of university employees on the development of the local community, as development leads to raising the efficiency of employees in all aspects of their work, whether teaching, scientific research, community service or administrative work, and achieving continuous development leads to the accumulation of experience over the years. Years, which makes them an effective tool in the development of society through their influence on students at the university.

Limitations of the study

The current study has the following limitations:

1. This population study consisted of Palestine technical university students.
2. The study carried out in the academic year (2022-2023) at the second semester.
3. The study was limited by the concepts and definitions mentioned in it.

Recommendations

In light of the results, the researcher recommended the following:

The need to continuously update the courses of study for members of the academic staff according to the needs of the community. That the academic staff member adopts in his scientific production contemporary research methodologies and methods that keep pace with the problems of contemporary society.

1. The need to encourage members of the academic staff to hold high-level training courses for members of the local community.
2. Allowing members of the academic staff to work as volunteers with local community institutions in order to benefit from their experiences as a form of professional development.
3. Allowing its specialized cadres to contribute to the development of local community institutions.
4. The need to conclude scientific and applied cooperation agreements with local community institutions.
5. The need to adopt strategic planning for professional development programs to raise the level of academic staff members in the field of scientific research.
6. The need to organize seminars and scientific conferences to solve the problems of society as a kind of professional development for members of the academic staff.

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